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THE PRINCIPLE OF GOOD FAITH IN MODERN CIVIL LAW

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ABSTRACT

This work is dedicated to a fundamental issue of civil law - the principle of good faith, specifically its application in judicial practice. The aim of this work is to review the importance of applying the principle of good faith in the development of such an essential field of civil law as judicial law. Additionally, it seeks to make a modest contribution to raising public awareness. The issues under consideration primarily pertain to the principle of good faith, which is critical in resolving disputes between parties.

Keywords: principle of good faith, civil law, judicial law, contract law, judicial practice.

Introduction

The principle of good faith is a foundational concept in modern law. It constitutes a significant institution of civil law, within which the realization of this principle serves as a basis for the development of judicial law. This is precisely why the principle of good faith is more or less represented across various fields of civil law.

The aim of this work is to review the importance of applying the principle of good faith in the development of such an essential field of civil law as judicial law. Additionally, it seeks to make a modest contribution to raising public awareness. The issues under consideration primarily pertain to the principle of good faith, which is critical in resolving disputes between parties.

The methodological foundation of the study includes general scientific, systematic, comparative, logical, and analytical methods.

The relevance of the topic arises from the purpose of the principle of good faith and its practical application. Apart from the introduction and conclusion, the work comprises several main sections, which provide a developed argument addressing the issues posed in the introduction and answering them in the conclusion.

Since the first part of the work serves as the introduction, attention will initially be focused on the second part, which addresses the general characterization of good faith. This part outlines the key issues necessary to determine the essence and definition of good faith. It also provides a brief historical overview of the origins of the concept of good faith. The third part of the work deals with the functions of good faith, whose primary objective is to achieve fair outcomes while avoiding clearly unjust results. This is directly linked to the stability and solidity of civil relationships. The fourth part discusses the development of judicial law through the application of the principle of good faith. Upholding the principle of good faith is crucial both during the conclusion of contracts and in their execution. In the event of a dispute between the parties, the court considers the good faith of the parties involved in the contractual relationship and often bases its decisions on this principle.

The conclusion of the work describes the outcomes that, due to their relevance, were highlighted during the research. Specifically, it presents the main summarizing theses, which are essential at the intersection of the principle of good faith and the development of judicial law.

General characterization of the principle of good faith

The principle of good faith is a universal evaluative category in private law [1, p. 83]. In certain cases, adherence to the principle of good faith determines the extent to which a party's expressed intent is deficient [2, p.65]. This principle delineates the boundaries of an individual's freedom of action, particularly when such boundaries do not directly arise from the specific legal relationship or the norms of law regulating that relationship [1, p.83].

Under the influence of the German Civil Code, this principle has been incorporated into various articles of the Georgian Civil Code [3, p.12]. Specifically, Article 8 [4], Paragraph 3 of the Georgian Civil Code states: "Participants in legal relationships are obligated to exercise their rights and fulfill their obligations in good faith." Additionally, Article 361 [4] of the Civil Code establishes the presumption of an obligation, with Paragraph 2 stipulating: "An obligation must be performed properly, in good faith, at the agreed time and place."

The diverse functions of the principle of good faith have led to its application in judicial law to achieve fair outcomes and simultaneously avoid clearly unjust results [3, p. 12]. Since the principle of good faith is a general obligation, it contributes to filling gaps in the proper regulation of social relationships. The principle of good faith serves as a guiding framework for the development of judicial law [5, p. 13].

The principle of good faith originates from Roman law. The principle of bona fides (good faith) held a significant place in ius civile and Roman legal thought. The use of the term bona fides (fides) in business relations implied that parties would honor their commitments and keep their word (bona fides negotia). Otherwise, the aggrieved party had the right to present an ex fide bona claim and demand the forced execution of the

obligation by invoking the *exceptio doli (generalis)* as the legal basis for the claim [6, p.5].

The principle of good faith is closely tied to moral standards. It is itself a moral standard - an ethical-legal principle [6, p.5] that can encompass justice, expediency, ethics, morality, and sincerity.

The principle of good faith applies to all types of private, public, and procedural legal relationships. Its core tenets include the following: participants in legal relationships must uphold the principle of trust during and after the fulfillment of obligations and approach each other's rights, property, and interests with respect and consideration [7, p.113]. The scope of application of the principle of good faith is primarily determined by cases where a claim formally aligns with existing substantive law but its enforcement would be unjust in the specific context. It is inadmissible for a right or outcome derived from existing law to be unjust. Accordingly, the principle of good faith opposes the exercise of rights that, in the given context, possess only the form of a right but lack substantive fairness [1, p.83].

Every legal order bases the rules of conduct for legal subjects on the principle of good faith and regards this principle as a normative concept. The institution of good faith is particularly significant in civil law, where it represents a fundamental principle of private law [8]. For example, in the law of sale, if a buyer does not request the rectification of a defect in an item or its replacement within the period granted to the seller for this purpose, nor seeks to terminate the contract, the buyer can demand a price reduction equivalent to the cost of rectifying the defect [4]. Under German regulations, the price reduction must take into account the extent to which the item's value has decreased due to the defect. In certain cases, the rectification of a defect may require disproportionate costs, even if the item's value has not substantially decreased due to the defect. Conversely, the item's value may decrease significantly because of the defect, yet the cost of rectifying the defect may be considerably less than the amount by which the item's value has been reduced. In such cases, it is important to assess the buyer's interest (specifically, whether their interest lies in rectifying the defect or retaining the defective item) and weigh the buyer's interest against that of the seller. Considering the specifics of a case, the court may go beyond the strict wording of the law and, when calculating the price reduction, rely on the principles of good faith and the preservation of equality and balance between the parties' interests [9, p.4].

According to the court's interpretation, civil legal relationships are based on the requirements of fairness, good faith, and morality. Accordingly, participants in legal relationships are obligated to exercise their rights and fulfill their obligations in good faith. Exercising a right in good faith includes adhering to a basic standard of prudence when expressing intent, ensuring that their unconsidered actions do not unjustly infringe upon the rights of others [10].

The principle of good faith in the contract law of European countries

The principle of good faith is characteristic of continental European legal systems and is foreign to common law countries. This principle urges contracting

parties to fulfill their mutual obligations in good faith - on the basis of trust and confidence [11, p.50].

In the Middle Ages, the principle of good faith evolved into a purely substantive legal norm within unified European law, becoming integrated into the concepts of fairness and equality, thereby gaining broader significance [12, p.16].

During the creation of civil codes, the principle of good faith retained its importance, thanks to the Natural Law School. It found expression in numerous codes. The principle of good faith had the greatest impact on the formation of German judicial thought and the processes of legal development. The prototype of *bona fide* in German law is *Treu und Glauben* (fidelity and trust), upon which German courts built entire volumes of precedents. Over time, these became the foundation for the establishment of new legal norms and values, significantly influencing the development of the doctrine of good faith in European codifications [13, p.18].

In 19th-century Europe, the first civil law act to reflect the principle of good faith was the French Civil Code of 1804. Article 1134 of the Code stipulates that "legally established agreements must be performed in good faith." Moreover, as early as the 17th and 18th centuries, French jurists identified good faith as one of the fundamental principles of the French civil law system. Specifically, according to the French jurist Domat, every person must be guided by this provision when fulfilling their obligations [5, p.16].

Another French jurist, Pothier, noted that contractual good faith prohibits all forms of deceit. Additionally, good faith limits the withholding of any information that could significantly impact the formation of a contract. For instance, concealing facts important to the other party for the purpose of deriving some benefit is contrary to the principle of good faith [14].

In early French law, a judge's free interpretation of a contract was considered an unacceptable intrusion into the freedom of the parties to express their will. Furthermore, it was remarked in France that good faith was a forgotten principle in French law, lacking practical significance and exerting no influence on legal relationships [15, 91f].

In 19th-century German law, great importance was attached to the concept of good faith (*Treu und Glauben*, meaning "loyalty and trust" in German). The term *Treu* signifies loyalty, commitment, and trustworthiness, while *Glauben* denotes faith and confidence. Good faith was considered a central category of obligations law [16, p.26]. In German legal doctrine, the principle of *Treu und Glauben* served as a fundamental tool through which the German Civil Code managed to address social, economic, and political challenges, particularly in the aftermath of World War II. This principle played a key role in preventing and remedying deficiencies that arose during this period [17, Vol. 61, 20].

The principle of *Treu und Glauben* is described as a "golden thread" running through the entire system of German obligations law and civil law, recognized for its significance in the application and interpretation of the norms of the German Civil Code and other legislative acts [5, p.23].

According to Paragraph 242 of the German Civil Code, "The obligor is required to perform in good faith, as demanded by the practices of commerce" [7, p.113]. The principle of good faith was acknowledged as a "royal norm," tasked with the "moralization" of German law, influencing and modifying other areas of law as well [3, p.12].

Paragraph 157 of the German Civil Code further stipulates that "Contracts must be interpreted based on the principle of good faith, considering the customary practices of commerce." This provision grants courts the authority to interpret contracts, a power that is actively exercised in practice.

In German legal doctrine, the principle of good faith has expanded beyond the realm of contract law, becoming a regulatory institution for other areas of law as well [18].

Similarly, Article 2 of the Swiss Civil Code explicitly states that the principle of good faith applies not only to contractual relationships but also to all civil legal relationships, serving as a governing norm for their regulation.

According to Articles 1337 and 1375 of the Italian Civil Code, parties are required to act in good faith not only during the performance of a contract but also during the pre-contractual negotiation stage [5, p.48].

According to Article 762, Section 2, of the Portuguese Civil Code, parties are obligated to act in good faith both during the performance of obligations and the exercise of rights [19].

In English law, the principle of good faith has not found the same widespread acceptance as in other European countries. In fact, there is a negative attitude towards good faith in English law. This negative stance towards the principle of good faith is expressed in four main ways: First, if a general principle is necessary, it should be established by Parliament at the legislative level, not by the courts; second, the use of the principle of good faith is seen as a violation of the principle of freedom of contract; third, English legal thought views the principle of good faith as setting non-legal (moral) criteria; and fourth, the principle of good faith is seen as creating legal uncertainty [20, p.161].

The English-language equivalent of good faith is divided into two parts. The first part, "Good Faith," is understood as a subjective concept of the principle (honesty), while the second part, "Fair Dealing," emphasizes the ethical criteria of the principle [21, p.258], suggesting that, given the inexperience of a beginner in a business relationship, it is better to make a choice in favor of an interpretation that benefits them [22, p.14]. "Good Faith and Fair Dealing" represents an objective standard of conduct, while "Good Faith" reflects an individual's subjective mental attitude toward their behavior, expressed in the ignorance of a fact.

The legislative and judicial practices of England and Ireland do not recognize the principle of good faith and do not have an associated doctrine, as the primary focus for them is to ensure that the law remains fully foreseeable and free from any unexpected elements [13, p.32]. A situation misjudged by a judge should not result in the violation of the parties' legal guarantees. It is because of this approach that English law rejects the

principle of good faith, placing the entire risk on the parties when entering into a legal relationship with each other. For English law, the existence of true rights is what matters, not their ethical aspects.

Despite the disregard for the principle of good faith, English law has developed special principles in the form of so-called implied terms, which often lead to the same outcomes as the application of the principle of good faith. For example, a judge is required to interpret a contract in a way that a reasonable person would understand it [13, p.34].

"In English law, the parties to a contract do not need to focus on mutual trust and confidence when performing the contract. Essentially, everything is decided by the plain wording of the contract, and it does no harm if one party uses its contractual rights unfairly or maliciously" [23, p.66-67].

It is also noteworthy that there is no unified opinion in English legal doctrine regarding what is meant by the concept of good faith. This further complicates the recognition and practical application of the principle.

The principle of good faith is still used in European law, but as an adjective ("in good faith"). Accordingly, "good faith" represents a limitation on how a party should fulfill its obligations and does not require a party to fulfill its obligation in a specific manner [24, p.5].

The principle of good faith is reflected in the 1980 Vienna Convention on Contracts for the International Sale of Goods, which includes a rule that good faith must be observed in international trade when interpreting the Convention. This provision does not impose an obligation on the parties to act in good faith. Article 7.1 of the Convention concerns the "interpretation" of the Convention and is directed more towards the courts than the parties. In other words, when interpreting the Convention, courts must uphold good faith in international trade [5, p.46].

The principle of good faith is also reflected in the principles of European contract law [25]. According to Article 1:102 of the Principles of European Contract Law, "the parties are free to conclude a contract and define its content in accordance with the principles of good faith and fairness, provided the contract does not conflict with any imperative rules set out in the 'Principles of European Contract Law' [26, p.19]. Article 1:106(1) of the Principles of European Contract Law states that "these principles should be interpreted and expanded in accordance with their objectives, giving attention to the principles of good faith and fairness, the mutual trust between the parties in contractual relationships, and consistent practices in the application of these principles" [26, p.20]. Additionally, according to Article 1:201 of the Principles of European Contract Law: 1. Each party must act in accordance with the principles of good faith and fairness. 2. The parties do not have the right to exclude or limit this obligation [26, p.21].

The principle of good faith and fair dealing is established in UNIDROIT [27, p.185] Principles of International Commercial Contracts, Article 1.7. According to Article 1.7 of UNIDROIT Principles of International

Commercial Contracts, "all parties must act in accordance with good faith and fair dealing in international trade." Moreover, the parties are not allowed to exclude or limit the obligation to act in accordance with this principle [5, p.47]. The principle of good faith is applied both in the performance of obligations and in the conclusion, validity, and interpretation of contracts.

One of the specific applications of the principle of good faith is the prohibition of contradictory conduct, which is reflected in UNIDROIT Principles, Article 1.8. According to this article, conduct that contradicts prior actions can invalidate a right, claim, or defense. A party's misrepresentation may result from their conduct or silence, when it is expected that they will assert a claim based on the mistake or misunderstanding that the other party has developed [28, p.37].

Article 1.8 of UNIDROIT Principles protects a party from harm caused by reliance on trust. It does not necessarily mean that a party who acts inconsistently should be restricted in their right to act in such a manner. This principle is merely a tool to prevent harm. For example, a party may act inconsistently if they have sent a notice to the other party within a reasonable period or compensated for the damage caused by relying on the trust [28, p.38].

It is noteworthy that UNIDROIT Principles, as well as the legal acts of various countries, contain numerous norms regulating the principle of good faith. This is logical, as every relationship in which parties find themselves begins with expectations of trust and good faith.

Norms containing the principle of good faith in the Georgian Civil Code

In contemporary Georgian legal practice, good faith is a material legal norm integrated into a legal system based on justice and equality, giving it a broader significance.

In addition to the aforementioned Articles 8 and 361 of the Georgian Civil Code, the Georgian Civil Code contains various norms that refer to the observance of the principle of good faith:

Article 5, paragraph 2 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"If the application of the analogy of law is not possible, the relationship must be regulated based on the general principles of law, as well as in accordance with the requirements of justice, good faith, and morality (analogy of law)."

Article 37, paragraph 2, first sentence of the Georgian Civil Code:

"A person (or persons) with management or representative powers must lead the case in good faith."

Article 55 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"An agreement is void if it was concluded by one party through the malicious use of influence over the other, when their relationship is based on special trust."

Article 81, paragraph 2 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"If one party remains silent due to circumstances under which the other party would not have expressed its will upon disclosure, the deceived party may demand the annulment of the transaction. The obligation of disclosure exists only when the party reasonably expected it in good faith."

Article 98 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"1. If the occurrence of a condition is hindered in bad faith by the party for whom the occurrence of the condition is not advantageous, the condition shall be deemed to have occurred;

2. If the occurrence of a condition is hindered in bad faith by the party for whom the occurrence of the condition is advantageous, the condition shall not be deemed to have occurred."

Article 104, paragraph 2 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"If a transaction is concluded on behalf of another person, the lack of representative authority may not be used by the other party to the transaction if the presented party created circumstances under which the other party reasonably believed such authority existed."

Article 159 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"A possessor is in good faith if they hold the item legally or if they may be considered an authorized person based on the necessary due diligence in business relations."

Article 187 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"1. The acquirer becomes the owner of the item even if the seller was not the owner of the item, provided the acquirer acts in good faith. The acquirer will not be considered to act in good faith if they knew or should have known that the seller was not the owner. The fact of good faith must exist before the item is transferred."

"2. A good faith acquirer cannot become the owner of the item if the item was lost by the owner, stolen from them, or otherwise left their possession against their will, or if the acquirer received it without consideration. These restrictions do not apply to money, securities, and items sold at auction."

Article 261, Paragraph 5 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"If the collateral consists of shares or a stake in a business entity, the pledgor must act in accordance with the principle of good faith, considering both their own interests and those of the pledgee, when making decisions related to the business entity or entering into transactions."

Article 285, Paragraph 2 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"In the case of unlawful sale of the collateral by the pledgee, the acquirer gains ownership rights if they act in good faith regarding the fact."

Article 346 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"A standard contractual clause is void, despite its inclusion in the contract, if it is detrimental to the other party and contrary to the principles of trust and good faith. In such cases, the circumstances under which the clause was included, the mutual interests of the parties, and other factors must be taken into account."

Article 609 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"The franchisee is obligated to pay a fee, the amount of which is essentially calculated based on the contribution to the implementation of the franchising system. The franchisee must act with the diligence of a good businessman, actively engaging in business, receiving services, and purchasing goods through the

franchisor or its designated individuals, provided that it is directly related to the purpose of the contract."

Article 610 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"When entering into a contract, the parties must disclose fully and openly to each other the circumstances related to the franchising business, especially the franchising system, and must provide each other with information in good faith. They are obligated not to disclose the entrusted information even if the contract is not concluded."

Article 731 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"The freight forwarder must dispatch the goods with the diligence of a good freight forwarder, select the participants in the shipment; at the same time, they must protect the interests of the sender and follow their instructions."

Article 765 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"If the deposit is gratuitous, the depositary is obligated to take care of the item with the same diligence as they would their own property."

Article 781 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"The warehouse keeper must perform the duties of receiving goods with the diligence of a good entrepreneur."

Article 935, Paragraph 2 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"Each participant has the right to request that all participants fulfill their duties in good faith arising from joint activity."

Article 969 of the Georgian Civil Code:

"A person (performer) who performs the tasks of another person (owner) without an order or other basis is obligated to carry them out in good faith."

In addition, the obligation to conduct private legal relationships in good faith is explicitly stated in several provisions of the Civil Code. While many provisions do not directly reference it, they are nonetheless based on this principle. In all of these cases, the parties must consider and adhere to the principle of good faith, as the Code imperatively emphasizes the protection of good faith.

In all of these cases, the principle of good faith must be taken into account and respected by the parties, as the Code imperatively emphasizes the protection of good faith.

The universality of the principle of good faith is a characteristic feature of civil law, and its application is found across various branches of civil law. For example, according to Article 50 of the Law of Georgia on Entrepreneurs [29], the head of a business entity is required to manage the affairs of the enterprise lawfully and with the diligence of a good leader. The Court of Cassation noted that the duties of a person authorized to lead a company can be divided into three parts: a) diligence, b) loyalty, and c) good faith [30]. As is known, the Delaware Supreme Court, which examined the case of CEDE - Technicolor, also formulated three duties of leadership: the duty of diligence (to act as a reasonable person would in the same position), the duty of loyalty (to act in the best interests of the corporation), and the principle of good faith [31].

A director or manager has an obligation to perform their functions in good faith before the corporation, in

such a way that they reasonably believe they are acting in the best interests of the corporation and with the diligence that a reasonable and prudent person in a similar position and under similar circumstances would exercise.

This illustrates that the principle of good faith is characteristic of civil law as a whole. Norms containing good faith are found both directly and indirectly in various articles of the Civil Code and serve to balance the parties' relations in business dealings, encouraging mutual consideration. Furthermore, for the relationship to bring benefit to each party, it must be based on trust between the parties. Without trust between the parties, it would be inappropriate to talk about good faith, as civil legal relations are founded on the principles of justice, good faith, and morality.

Functions of the principle of good faith

To understand the essence of good faith, it is necessary to explore its functions. The primary function of the principle of good faith is to ensure just outcomes and, at the same time, to prevent clearly unjust outcomes, which is directly related to the stability and reliability of civil relations [32]. The concretization of the principle of good faith occurs through the following functions: the function of extension, the function of imposing limitations, and the function of correction [7, p.113].

The function of extension implies that the clarification of existing primary contractual obligations should be done in accordance with the principle of good faith. New additional obligations to the contract, which serve to ensure the execution of the contract or the protection of the parties, arise considering the principle of good faith [7, p.113]. If the contract does not contain a certain term, the gap in the contract must be filled by an additional explanation of the agreement [3, p.54]. In this case, it is about restoring objectivity in contractual relations in such a way that specific rules are established for the parties, regardless of the content of their will [5, pp.81-82]. The Federal Court of Germany has explained this function as follows: "The judge is required to reveal and consider everything that the parties did not disclose, but which, considering the ultimate purpose of the contract, should have been included, had the gaps been filled in accordance with the principles of justice and the customs of business transactions"[33, p.91].

The court decision from which this quote is extracted was made in the following case: Two doctors living in small provincial towns agreed to exchange their places of residence in order to expand their practice. Nine months after the agreement, one of the doctors returned to their original location and resumed their practice there. The second doctor disagreed with this because they feared competition: their clients might return to the long-time familiar doctor. The agreement did not include any provisions on the prohibition of such activities, nor was there any such regulation in the norms of dispositive law. As a result, the Federal Supreme Court of Germany resorted to "additional interpretation of the contract" to fill the gap. Through this method, the court deemed it possible to add supplementary regulatory norms to the contract, according to

which both doctors were prohibited from maintaining a permanent practice near their previous locations for two to three years [33, p.91].

The purpose of the function of extension is to properly allocate the risks of unforeseen and unregulated circumstances between the parties to the contract, in accordance with the trading customs of the given area. The judge should not forget that the court's considerations are only to be taken into account to the extent necessary to resolve the specific issue at hand [3, p.54].

The function of imposing limitations refers to situations where the principle of good faith creates an inherent (inseparable) framework for the exercise of existing rights [7, p.113]. The principle of good faith is essential to limit the boundaries of rights exercised under the contract. The function of limiting rights is implemented through the direct application of Articles 115 and 361 of the Civil Code of Georgia, which is justified by Paragraph 3 of Article 8 of the Civil Code in both cases [5, p.91]. The restrictive function is synonymous with the function of imposing limitations and is manifested in the balancing of the interests of the parties involved and the limitation of the unjust use of rights [34, p.66]. This function of limitation can also be applied when a person unfairly obstructs the creation of a right or unfairly exploits the trust granted to them [5, p.91].

The principle of good faith imposes on the parties the obligation to consider each other's interests when fulfilling contractual obligations. If a party uses its rights in a way that violates the duty to consider the interests of the other party, such use of the right should be regarded as an abuse of rights [5, pp.92-93].

The corrective (or rectifying) function refers to situations where, in the case of complex and long-term legal relationships, significant modifications to rights and obligations may occur, and the content of the rights and obligations of the parties within the specific relationship may be redefined [5, p.95]. In such cases, the principle of good faith can be used to adapt legal relations to the changed circumstances.

Any legal system takes into account how to resolve issues regarding the continued performance of obligations in light of changed circumstances. Changed circumstances are usually those determined by judicial practice. A change in circumstances makes performance more difficult to the extent that demanding performance, no matter how justified the other party's claims might be, contradicts the requirements for the fair exchange of benefits and the principle of good faith characteristic of civil turnovers [35, pp. 399–400].

In accordance with the principle of good faith, the court has the authority to modify the contractual legal relationship between the parties. This function becomes apparent when the court intervenes in the agreement between the parties due to changes in society that affect the existence and continuation of the contractual legal relationship [5, p.94]. This approach is reflected in Paragraph 313 of the German Civil Code, which addresses changes in the basis of a transaction and sets out various cases for adapting a contract to changed circumstances.

The main function of the principle of good faith is not to create a confrontation between the interests of the parties, but rather to establish their solidarity, which forms the foundation of normal civil turnover. Good faith is not only a presumption of the existence of a right, but also a presumption of the fulfillment of an obligation.

Good faith refers to the actions of participants in civil turnover who act responsibly and treat each other's rights with respect. Good faith is both a normative and subjective instrument for interpreting will. Based on it, both legal and contractual defects are eliminated. The content of the principle of good faith is primarily expressed by the obligation of a party, in addition to fulfilling the obligation properly, to fulfill it in good faith, meaning to consider and protect the legitimate interests of the other party. Violation of this requirement can serve as grounds for imposing liability not only during the process of fulfilling the contractual obligation, but also during contractual negotiations and subsequent stages of fulfilling the main obligations [36].

The principle of good faith as the basis for the development of judicial practice

The state creates abstract legal norms that are intended for repeated use and are aimed at regulating individual situations. If the administration of justice were reduced to the mechanical application of the law and judges had no freedom, in such a case we could reliably predict the outcome of any legal dispute, and it would be impossible for judicial decisions to contradict each other. Only in the judicial process can a legal norm develop fully and be understood in its full meaning [37, p.69].

According to Article 63 of the Constitution of Georgia, "A judge is independent in his/her work and is subject only to the Constitution and the law." Based on this constitutional provision, we must conclude that the fundamental law prohibits judicial law as a source of law [38, p.132].

In continental European countries, when a judge applies the abstract norms of the code, they specify, supplement, and correct them based on the specific case. This is nothing more than legal creation. Thus, a judge who applies the law is, at the same time, creating it. Gone are the days when Montesquieu said, "The law speaks through the mouth of the judge"[3, p.24].

Judicial law should be understood, on one hand, as the application, interpretation, and comprehension of legal norms, and, on the other hand, judicial law represents the collective body of all judicial decisions that establish the meaning of legal norms. Judicial law is the collection of court decisions on the resolution of relationships that are unregulated by positive legal norms or judicial precedents [39, p.68]. Judicial law is an act of applying the law, not law-making. Its practical significance comes into play when judicial decisions fill legislative gaps [38, p.133].

The principle of good faith is a norm that modifies other norms. Associate Professor, Judge Alexander Ioseliani develops the following thoughts regarding the principle of good faith: "The responsibility for the non-application of the principle of good faith should not escape the corps of the Georgian judiciary, especially

those judges who have been handling civil disputes for years, particularly when considering the fact that the disproportionate increase in the role of the principle of good faith in Germany was caused by the very activity of the courts" [3, p.14]. "A judge should not seek to determine the initial intent of the legislators but should think about how best to interpret the law in the present situation. A judge must always proceed from the current reality in order to regulate specific legal relations more adequately and justly" [40, p76].

The best example of the court's application of the principle of good faith is the decision made by the German Imperial Supreme Court on November 28, 1923, when the court took responsibility and rejected the principle of nominalism in relation to the German mark. Specifically, the court itself determined the exchange rate of the German mark. After World War I, Germany was experiencing hyperinflation. The unchecked inflation led to wealth redistribution, economic difficulties, and social disorder. Despite various proposals for finding a solution to the difficult situation, only Oertmann's theory [3, p.62] of the "basis of the agreement" was accepted by the German Imperial Court, which relied on Paragraph 242 of the German Civil Code. By applying this theory, the court adapted contracts to the changed circumstances. Based on this theory, the German Supreme Court began making large-scale precedent decisions, recognizing its role in the protection of social justice [3, pp.25-26]. This approach was grounded in the view that each obligational relationship, taking into account exceptional circumstances, should be examined to determine whether there is, and if so, to what extent, a revaluation of the creditor's claims [5, p.22].

The case concerned the performance of an obligation arising before the start of World War I (before hyperinflation), where the debtor decided to fulfill the obligation with paper marks, which had become completely devalued by the time of performance. The court ruled that the debtor had failed to fulfill the obligation. It determined the exchange rate of the German mark itself. The court faced a dilemma: if the principle of nominalism were applied, it would result in a substantially damaging outcome for the creditor, contrary to the principle of justice. The devaluation of the mark created a conflict between the principle of nominalism and the principle of good faith. The German Imperial Court applied Section 242 of the German Civil Code and gave precedence to the principle of good faith in its decision [3, pp.27-28].

The court, within its discretion, interprets the principle of good faith. To some extent, good faith can be seen as a prerequisite for imposing an obligation. In one case, the Supreme Court of Georgia clarified that the starting point for the norms regulating civil law relationships is the restoration of natural justice. Accordingly, in civil law relations, the standard of behavior is defined by justice, good faith, and morality. In the case, the cassation party created a trust factor for entering into the contract based on undisputed factual circumstances, and by failing to formalize the contract, the principle of good faith was violated. In this regard, the cassation court points out that within the framework of contractual freedom, the assumption that the contract is

considered concluded before it is signed is less justified according to the provisions of the Civil Code (Article 327). However, in cases where the form of the contract is mandatory, such an assumption does not create an obligation to conclude the contract [41].

According to the court's interpretation, the principle of good faith primarily involves considering the interests of the individual, and in the absence of this, the abuse of rights occurs. It serves as an evaluative criterion in civil law, through which, by distinguishing between what is just and unjust, the individual arrives at the most just decision based on the evaluation of an objective observer. The principle of good faith in Georgian judicial practice is considered directly applicable law and a legal basis for claims, with the goal of achieving just outcomes and preventing unjust ones. The application of the principle of good faith becomes relevant when a person's claim or action formally complies with existing substantive legislation, but its implementation in a specific case is unjust. Therefore, its function is clearly to prevent unjust results, which is directly related to the stability and integrity of civil relationships [42].

The application of the principle of good faith in Georgian court practice

In Georgian court practice, there are judicial decisions, including in the first instance courts, where judges have applied the principle of good faith and based their decisions on this principle.

The Civil Chamber of the Supreme Court of Georgia made an important clarification regarding the creditor's and debtor's relationship, addressing the misuse of the creditor's rights as a result of the breach of the duty of good faith and consideration [43]. The Cassation Chamber explained that, in general, the conduct of all subjects of law is based on the principle of good faith, and this principle is considered a normative concept. It is one of the fundamental principles of modern law, philosophy, and business. Good faith entails acting responsibly and treating the rights of others with respect in civil circulation. It is both a normative and a subjective instrument for interpreting will. It eliminates defects in the law and in contracts. The content of the principle of good faith is primarily expressed in that a party is required not only to properly perform their obligations but also to do so in good faith, which includes considering and protecting the legitimate interests of the contracting party. A violation of this requirement can be the basis for liability, not only during the performance of contractual obligations but also during contractual negotiations and after the performance of the main obligations.

Additionally, the Supreme Court of Georgia noted that in all legal relationships in which the state participates, the level of trust and good faith is particularly high. In such cases, there should be no issue in broadly interpreting and applying the principle of good faith [44].

The Supreme Court pointed out the concept of good faith in one of its decisions [45] and explained that participants in a legal relationship are obligated to exercise their rights and obligations in good faith. The

duty to act in good faith is based on the general presumption of good faith in law. The primary basis for forming a contract should not be the opposition of the participants' interests, but rather their solidarity towards each other. Moreover, the principle of good faith serves as both a normative and a subjective instrument for interpreting will, which also implies that although the conduct of the contracting party should comply with the formally applicable material law or the terms of the contract, its implementation in specific cases should not be unjust or contradict the other party's reasonable trust. The principle of good faith essentially requires the contracting party to consider the interests of the other party.

In line with the spirit of the Georgian Civil Code, which also reflects the public order of Georgia, the principle of the freedom to enter into contracts is complemented by the principles of good faith and contractual fairness, on the basis of which new behavioral norms or standards can be established. Law consists of principles and rules guided by a sense of fairness among the parties. Therefore, every person, in exercising their rights and obligations, must act in accordance with these principles. The principle of good faith considers a person's actions in relation to the criterion of fairness. According to this principle, a participant in a legal relationship is obliged to distinguish between what is fair and what is unjust, and to align their behavior with the criterion of fairness. This means that their behavior must be perceived as fair by an objective observer or an unbiased person [46].

The obligation of a participant in the legal relationship to properly fulfill their obligation is based on the reality known to them, and they are required to have a good faith attitude toward this reality. The obligation to act in good faith is based on the general presumption of good faith in law [47].

By applying the principle of good faith, the court protected the interests of the insured, the weaker party in the insurance relationship. The panel concluded that the insurance relationship between the parties was terminated, and as a result, the insurer no longer has the right to demand payment of the insurance premium. While civil legislation allows the insurer to claim compensation for damages resulting from contract termination, this was not the subject of the dispute in the present case.

In one of the cases, the court emphasized the relationship between good faith and legality, stating that both must be upheld when a person exercises their rights. Furthermore, it noted that the abuse of an owner's rights is not only prohibited by law but also constitutes a moral obligation for the owner. Abuse of rights is equated with situations where a person does not exercise a right solely to harm another, or where inaction serves no purpose in protecting an interest essential to the exercise of that right [48].

The Baghdati Magistrate Court, applying the principle of good faith, reduced the claimant's demand for loan interest under a loan agreement on its own initiative, declaring the agreement between the parties regarding the annual market interest rate as void. The

court further noted that the claimant was engaged in entrepreneurial activity and represented the economically stronger party. Considering this fact, the court found that the claimant acted in bad faith by setting an excessively high interest rate [49].

When the principle of contractual freedom conflicts with the principle of good faith, priority should be given to the principle of good faith, as it is this principle that ensures a fair balance between the rights and obligations of the parties to a contract. The principle of good faith serves the function of balancing the rights and obligations of the parties, requiring participants in civil transactions to act with respect and consideration for each other's rights [5, p.111]. This principle also fosters the development of civil law, as in the hands of a judge, it becomes a measure of justice that enables fair decisions based on both the law and the judge's inner conviction.

Regarding judicial discretion [50, p.73], an interesting perspective is offered by Aharon Barak, former President of the Supreme Court of Israel, who argues that judicial lawmaking is the court's authority to choose between several lawful alternatives [50, p.72].

Law is an abstract norm, and only through a court's decision does the legislator's rule become a binding act that applies to society. Judges give the law its real and concrete form. Therefore, it can be said that a statute ultimately crystallizes into the form given to it by the judge [50, p.73].

The role and influence of judicial practice are steadily growing, even in countries adhering to continental European legal traditions. Social relations are changing dynamically and rapidly, and judicial practice facilitates the adaptation of the law to these evolving relationships [38, p.166].

Conclusion

The principle of good faith has a long history, originating from Roman law, where it held a significant place in Roman legal thought.

Both in doctrine and at the legislative level, the principle of good faith, either directly or indirectly, is firmly established across various branches of civil law. This principle is reflected in numerous articles of the Civil Code of Georgia and plays a crucial role within the civil law system.

The principle of good faith is aimed at balancing and harmonizing the interests of contractual parties and should play a leading role in the development of judicial practice.

Since the Civil Code does not provide a definition of good faith, this principle represents an open norm, meaning it is an indefinite legal category used to achieve fair outcomes and to avoid clearly unjust results. The principle of good faith serves to fill gaps in the law and contracts, enabling courts to make decisions and establish legal protection mechanisms without violating the law. The existence of gaps in the law requires judicial supplementation, which presents an excellent opportunity for the development of judicial law.

The inclusion of the principle of good faith in the Principles of European Contract Law has further expanded its application. Every contract and its content

must be based on expectations of fairness and good faith, which allow parties to make their business relationships more stable.

The principle of good faith constitutes a general obligation and is itself a moral standard. Good faith implies sincerity, impartiality, objectivity, and fairness, presuming that every party to a civil relationship will perform their rights and obligations in good faith.

The bona fide principle is a universal phenomenon characteristic of various legal systems and is aimed at fostering common legal tendencies. Even in English law, where the principle of good faith does not receive distinct emphasis, the so-called implied terms principle exists. This principle is often applied to achieve the same outcomes as the principle of good faith serves in the legislative acts of other countries.

The principle of good faith gains significant importance in the hands of the court when specific norms prove deficient in resolving contractual legal relationships. In such cases, by utilizing the functions of the principle of good faith, the court makes decisions and fills the gaps in the law or the contract. Each such decision contributes to the development of judicial law, as the court addresses legislative omissions, interprets the law, and finds new ways to apply it.

While the principle of contractual freedom allows parties to enter into agreements as they wish, there are instances where such contracts may be interpreted differently by the court. The principle of autonomy of will is a fundamental achievement of civil law, but the court intervenes in the interpretation of agreements entered into by the parties only within the boundaries of the law and reasonableness. This does not mean that a judge has the right to make arbitrary decisions or circumvent the law. A judge must interpret specific legal ambiguities and deliver a fair decision only when necessary, considering the requirements of good faith.

The Civil Code of Georgia does not contain a provision that explicitly mandates the interpretation of contracts based on the requirements of good faith. The inclusion of such a norm would further strengthen the development of judicial law, as it would allow for contract interpretation to consider the customs of civil turnover, as referenced in paragraph 157 of the German Civil Code. Nevertheless, various articles of the Civil Code of Georgia clearly emphasize the requirement to uphold the principle of good faith between parties. These articles are scattered throughout different sections of the Civil Code and, in addition to serving as general provisions, also function as norms governing specific legal relationships.

The legislation of many European countries explicitly extends the principle of good faith to all civil law relationships. For example, Article 2 of the Swiss Civil Code explicitly states that the principle of good faith applies not only to contractual relationships but also to norms regulating all civil law relationships.

The principle of good faith should not be applied in isolation; it should enable broad judicial intervention in contractual relationships through judicial law. In the hands of a judge, the principle of good faith becomes a tool to protect the weaker party, aimed at maintaining balance between the parties. In some cases, ensuring

such balance may even raise the question of contract invalidity. For instance, if there is an obvious disproportion between the performance stipulated in a contract and the compensation agreed upon, and the contract was entered into because one party exploited the difficult circumstances or inexperience of the other, the realization of the principle of good faith could lead to the invalidation of such an agreement.

In recent years, Georgian judicial practice has seen an increase in cases where courts have made decisions based on the principle of good faith. Of particular importance are the decisions of the Supreme Court of Georgia and the Georgia Court of Appeals, as the development of law is driven by high-level courts with responsibilities far greater than merely determining facts. The decisions made by first-instance courts, in which the principle of good faith is invoked to fill gaps in laws and contracts, are also commendable. Such decisions primarily contribute to balancing the interests of the parties and simultaneously lay the groundwork for the development of judicial practice.

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